

NAME: Sindy Poppitz

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1. Segmental & Phonotactic Patterns (edges vs. internal)

Consonants:

--b, d, g, j only in Spanish loans

--glottal stop word-initial only before Vs

--voiceless stops, except tz, ch, tx (affricates), all except ʔ are usually aspirated in all positions

--voiced stops after juncture and after homorganic nasals and lateral

--f only in 2 native roots, where the cluster ʔf (/f/) = alternate for b' (/bʔ/)

--all Cs in the environments JVC, VCV, VCCV and VCJ (J = juncture)

--with the exception that b, d, g, and j not occur in VCJ,

--and h not as second C in VCCV

--some C-clusters in VCCV are morphophonemically replaced by a single C (see below)

→ e.g. of b' in these positions: *b'aj* 'bone', *lab'a* 'snake', *xib'te* 'frighten someone', *wetb'i* 'my companion', *t'eb'b'a* 'make naked above the waist', *ñab'* 'rain'

--all C-clusters of local dialect of Spanish are borrowed into Jacaltec (not enumerated here)

--Spanish nonsyllabic vocoids are borrowed as y and w, and often occur in C-clusters: *Dyos* 'God' (Span. *Dios*), *Consepsyón* (name of town; Span. *Consepción*), *twáya* 'towel' (Span. *toalla*)

--all nonloan JCC clusters begin with one of the sibilants s, ʃ, or x

--any C may occur as the second member, except that s'- and ʃ'- have not been noted (e.g. *sti' naj* 'his mouth', *ʃto naj* 'he goes', *xto naj* 'he went', *x'ahaw* 'moon')

--JCCC clusters are of two types: (1) Spanish loans with JCC preceded by the third person possessor prefix s-: *stwáya naj* 'his towel', and (2) transitive verbs with an unreduced pair of sibilant prefixes (reduction is optional, see below): *xsmak' naj* 'he hit something'

Vowels:

--all Vs in the environments CVC, CVJ, and CVVC: *ʃap* 'Sebastián' *ta* 'if', *yitail* 'its food'

--a few Vs have been noted in CVVJ, where the second V is a suffix: *xui* 'it happened'

2. "Rules" Part 1

Loss of final 'ʔ and j:

--when ʔ occurs before open juncture it is optionally lost: *hune' naj*, or *hune naj* 'a man'; *te' te'*, or *te te'* 'the tree'

--j before any juncture is optionally lost: *naj winaj*, or *na winaj*, or *na wina* 'the man'

Sibilant and affricate clusters:

(A) initial sibilant and affricate clusters

--initial clusters of two or three sibilants (s, ʃ, x) or one or two sibilants followed by an affricate (tz, ch, tx, tz', ch', tx') often occur

--the morphemes involved are x- past, ʃ- nonpast, s- third person verb subject or noun possessor, and any stem with an initial sibilant or affricate; the order of occurrence is tense-person-stem.

--these clusters optionally, but usually, undergo a cyclic series of regressive assimilation as to position of articulation and, in the case of sibilant clusters, reduction:

(1) the next-to-last sibilant may take on the position of articulation of the last sibilant or affricate (e.g. $\ddot{x}sx-$ > $\ddot{x}xx-$, $sch-$ > $\ddot{x}ch-$)

(2) if the last C is a sibilant, the resulting geminate cluster may be reduced (e.g. $\ddot{x}xx-$ > $\ddot{x}x-$)

(3) if the original cluster had three Cs, steps 1 and 2 reapply to the remaining two-C-cluster (e.g. $\ddot{x}x-$ > $xx-$ > $x-$)

→ homophony often results, as when x s- past-third person and \ddot{x} s- nonpast-third person both reduce to s-

--e.g. *ssat*, *sat* 'its face', *scheh*, $\ddot{x}cheh$ 'its horse', *stx'otx'*, *xtx'otx'* 'its dirt'

(B) sibilants and affricate reduction across juncture

--similarly to the initial clusters, morphophonemic change takes place when sibilants and affricates are separated by + juncture in compound nouns and after *mach* 'not, there is not'

--these alternations are obligatory

--the clusters noted all have ch as the first C, but the process probably applies to other Cs as well

--the cluster is reduced to a single affricate with the position and manner of articulation of the second C, the juncture is lost

--e.g. *mach swalil* > *matzsalil* 'he has no character', *yich tzow* > *yitzow* 'Under the amate tree (place name)', *mach stomo* > *matztomo* 'it doesn't cut something'

C-h cluster reduction:

--h is optionally, but usually, lost in the environment JCh, where C is always a sibilant: *sho'* vs. *so'* 'fifth'

--in noninitial C-h clusters, h is always lost: *x-hitx'-h-oni* > *xhitx'oni*, *xitx'oni* 'it made noise of wind blowing in the trees'

Geminate cluster reduction:

--some intervocalic geminate clusters are reduced

--the conditions for reduction are not understood; all available examples are given below

--on the other hand, the unreduced clusters b'b', nn, $\ddot{n}\ddot{n}$, and ll occur in the corpus

--e.g. *tzet-taj* > *tzetaj* 'what? (plural)', *i'-!-on-a \ddot{n}* > *i'on \ddot{n}* 'stutter!', *x-sis-s-oni* > *xisisoni* 'it hissed'

Affricate-' clusters:

--the cluster ch-' is always replaced by a single sound ch'

--it seems probably that other affricate-' clusters reduce in the same way, but no examples have been found

--e.g. *x-'uch-'-oni* > *x'uch'oni* 'it churned', *ch-'il-ot* > *ch'ilot* 'it is seen'

Assimilation of n:

--n takes on the position of articulation of a following bilabial or velar stop, i.e. it alternates with m and \ddot{n}

--in some cases, under conditions not understood, the assimilation is optional

--e.g. *ten-b'a* > *tenb'a*, *temb'a* 'pile up sth!', *hun-c'al* > *hu \ddot{n} c'al* 'twenty'

--n is also assimilated across + juncture, but always optionally: *xcan+canoj*, *xca \ddot{n} +canoj* 'it remained once and for all'

O in suffixes and clitics:

- in any suffix or postposed clitic with the V o, o > u when the preceding V is u
- the change is optional, but usual
- related to this is the fact that there are no suffixes of clitics whose base forms have u
- e.g. *chin hul-øj* > *chin huluj* 'I will arrive', *tzujl-ob'al* > *tzujlob'al*, *tzujlub'al* 'instrument for lighting fire', *ñus+toj* > *ñus+tuj* 'burn it up!' (toj is a clitic)

The morphophoneme H:

- one set of person-marking prefixes has two sets of allomorphs: one which occurs with 'initial stems and one which occurs before other stems
- a few h-initial stems take the pre-' set of prefixes (here H-initial)
- thus, all ' and H-initial stems take one set of prefixes, and all other stems - including h-initial - take the other set
- contrast the homophonic pairs *hak'b'al* 'candle' and *Hak'b'al* 'flower', and *hala* 'braid sth.' and *Hala* 'say sth.':
- hin hak'b'al* 'my candle', *wak'b'al* 'my flower'; *lañan hin halni* 'I'm braiding sth.', *lañan walni* 'I'm saying sth.'

Suffix-initial h:

- some suffixes and clitics of the form -V and -VC are optionally, esp. in careful speech, preceded by h when they follow a V; e.g. *ǰmunla-øj naj* > *ǰmunlaoj naj*, *ǰmunlahoj naj* 'he will work', *co sinta-an* > *co sintaan*, *co sintahan* 'our ribbon'
- in contrast, some suffixes never take h after a V-final stem: *xcha-ot naj* > *xchaot naj* 'he was found'

Root alternates:

- the final C of many roots with a CVC base form or alternate varies among some selection of ' , b' , h , w , y , and zero when the root takes a derivational suffix or occurs in a particular construction
- the suffixes are often nonproductive and often not truly analyzable as suffixes
- the two roots show alternations between b' and 'f → in *lab'* 'to have a supernatural experience', b' is replaced by 'f whenever a -V or -VC suffix follows: *xla'fi naj* 'he had a supernatural experience' (the root for 'two' *cab'* - *ca*, takes the alternate only in *ca'fi* 'two days ago')
- the only two transitive verbs having base forms with final ' , *ja* 'take, receive, carry sth.' and *a'a* 'put, give sth.', lose the ' when followed by any clitic, whether in normal transition or across open juncture
- e.g. *al+toj* 'put sth. down there!' (-*l* 'down, *toj* 'there'), *a+toj* 'put sth. there!'
- a few CVC words with final h optionally lost it: *hah* 'double armspan', *huh* 'someone', *heh* 'all right'

3. "Rules" Part 2

STRESS:

- stress distribution: (1) obligatory on the first syllable of most stems, (2) on the syllable before a contour except in emphatic sentences and yes-no questions, and (3) on a lexically determined syllable of some polysyllabic loans
- termed: stem-initial stress, precontour stress, and lexical stress

Stem-initial stress:

- stress occurs on the first syllable of each sstem in an utterance, including monosyllabic

stems, except that most particles (a stem class) are not stressed: *ch'ócojtoj hin mám≠b'oj wúxtaján* 'my father and my brother will go in there' (*b'oj* 'and' is an unstressed particle; *hin* vs. *w-* 'my' is a person-marker prefix; *≠* is an utterance juncture)

Precontour stress:

--sentences which lack precontour stress (stress on the last syllable before the final #-contour combination) are emphatic or are yes-no questions

--other sentences take precontour

--in some examples below *tu* 'that' is a particle which does not take stem-initial stress but which can take precontour stress

e.g. *xtó no' wácax tú* 'that cow went', *xtó no' wácax tu* 'did that cow go! / that cow went!'

--in three contexts the difference between the presence and absence of stress on a precontour syllable is neutralized; if the precontour syllable is also one which takes stem-initial stress (i.e. is a monosyllabic nonparticle stem with no suffix or postposed clitic), it is always stressed: *cach tó máy* 'may you went this morning./?!', cf. *cach tó éwí* 'you went yesterday', *cach to éwi* 'you went yesterday?/!'

Lexical stress:

--sometimes stress is lexically part of the stem and cannot be predicted from any other criteria

--two kinds of stems have lexical stress

--most particles are unstressed unless they take precontour stress

--a few are lexically stressed; some are *tó* 'it's the case that', *xín* 'then' (Spanish *pues*), and the negative particles *mát* and *mách* 'not' → stress on the negative particle is optional; the others are always stressed

e.g. *ta tó chin tóyí*,... 'if it's the case that I go...'

--second, lexical stress occurs with many polysyllabic loans; it corresponds to stress in the source language

--a stem with lexical stress on a nonfinal syllable and without a suffix or postposed clitic never takes precontour stress

--if the stem is suffixed or has a clitic, precontour stress can occur as for native stems; the initial syllable takes stem-initial stress, as for any other stem

e.g. *éscaléra* 'ladder./?!', *ha wéscaléra tú* 'that ladder of yours'

--when lexical stress falls on initial syllable of stem, it is phonologically indistinguishable from stem-initial stress, only difference, that final syllable never takes precontour stress!

e.g. *xtó ánma* 'the people went./?!', *hin síntha* 'my ribbon./?!', *sínthaé* 'ribbon'

--when a stem without suffix or postposed clitic has lexical stress on the final syllable and occurs before contour, the syllable is always stressed: *húne' lúgár* 'a place./?!', *húne' lúgár tú* 'that place'

--the semantic distinction between the presence and absence of precontour stress is neutralized for stems with lexical stress, unless they take a suffix or postposed clitic

4. Morpho-Syntax

STEMS AND ROOTS:

--Jacaltec morphemes of three major types: roots, clitics, and affixes

--a stem = a root, a root with one or more derivational affixes, a root or derived stem with a stem formative suffix, or a compound formed from these

--most stems may take inflectional prefixes and suffixes

--stems and inflected stems may be accompanied by clitics

- with one exception, each root class is matched by a stem class (exception are onomatopoetic roots)
- members of these root classes may occur without derivation as stems of the corresponding class, sometimes with a semantically empty stem formative suffix (the reverse is not true: there are stem classes which are not matched by single root classes)
- many positional roots (there are no derived positional stems) are also transitive verb roots
- a few stems are both intransitive and transitive verbs; all are stems derived by nonproductive suffixes or having final -CV which bespeaks a former suffix no longer analyzable as such

Onomatopoetic roots:

- only root class not matched by a stem class; occur only in derived verb and bound adverbial stems; often members of more than one root class and often keep their onomatopoetic connotations; usually represent sounds, but sometimes motions, textures, etc.

Verbs:

- transitive and intransitive verbs typically occur with a tense-person prefix in the verb phrase of sentences
- intr. take one person marker prefix, as subject: *c[ach] wayi* '[you] slept' (*cach* is the "prefix")
- trans. take subject and object person marker prefixes: *c[ach]₁ [hin]₂ mak'an* '[I]₂ hit (past) [you]₁' (*cach hin* is the "prefix") → although an object person marker is optional with the trans. verb, the stems always carry the connotation of both an actor and a goal

Statives:

- statives typically occur in noun and adverb phrases and as stative verb complements
- adjectives and positionals occur only as stative verb complements and in compound nouns (productively and non-productively derived)

Bound adverbials:

- follow verbs in verb phrases; most derived from verb, positional, or onomatopoetic stems

STEM FORMATIVE SUFFIXES:

- i vs. -yi: intr. stem formative; -yi only after Vs; -i only after Cs;
 - the suffix occurs on intrans. and pseudointrans. trans. (trans. with -n) stems which lack inflectional suffixes or postposed clitics, on some bound adverbials, and on the copula -eyi (with root -e)
 - always occurs on these stems when they immediately precede a contour; in other environments it is found only on stems which terminate in a CC cluster or C followed by the intr. derivational suffix -∅
- a- vs. -o vs. -u: trans. stem formative only in trans. verb roots if the form CVC, and only before contour in the absence of an inflectional suffix or postposed clitic
 - o and -u when the preceding root V is o and u; -a when the root V is i, e, or a
- an: positional stem formative on positional stems (which are always roots) in all environments except when the reduplicative distributive plural suffix occurs
- a: stem formative on three irregular roots (*maca* 'who?', someone'; *hune* 'it's a man that'; *cach tita* 'you came')

INFLECTIONAL AFFIXES:

Person Markers:

--used with verb and most stative stems; occur pre- or postposed to these stems
 --two classes: PMA and PMB; PMA always prefixed to the stem, always immediately precedes the stem; PMB either prefixed or suffixed
 --PMA have two sets of allomorphs; example of PMA as noun possessor, with *oje* 'foot' and *b'i* 'name':

woj 'my foot', *ha woj* 'your foot', *yoj* 'its foot, their feet', *joj* 'our feet', *he yoj* 'you-all's feet'

hin b'i 'my name', *ha b'i* 'your name', *sb'i* 'its name, their names', *co b'i* 'our names', *he b'i* 'you-all's names'

→ set 1 allomorphs occur with '- or H-initial stems; these are lost after the PM

→ set 2 allomorphs are used before all other Cs

→ initial h of all PMA is lost after a C in normal transition

--PMB either before or after the stem: 1. when a tense or aspect marker occurs with a verb, PMB follows this; 2. when both PMA and PMB occur with a stem, they occur in the order PMB-PMA-stem; 3. when neither tense, aspect, or PMA occur, PMB is suffixed to the stem or to the stem already inflected by other suffixes

Tense and aspect markers; tense-person prefix:

--the aspect markers are particles which occur preposed to verbs which lack a tense prefix
 --they function like tense prefixes, but differ in several ways: (1) verbs with aspect markers are negated differently than verbs with tense prefixes; (2) transitive verbs with aspect markers require the pseudointransitive suffix *-n*; (3) intransitive verbs with aspect markers take PMA subject prefixes rather than PMB

--proclitics sometimes occur within the tense-person prefix → the tense prefix allomorphs *chi-* and \emptyset (nonpast) and *xma-*, *ma-*, and \emptyset (past) are used only when proclitics are present

--form of the tense-person prefix (positions numbered for reference): 1. *x-* (past), *ch-* (nonpast), *lañan* (continuative), *cat* (postsequentive), *lahwi* (presequentive); (2. possible proclitic); 3. *c-* (past); 4. PMB; (5. possible proclitic); 6. PMA

→ 3. *c-* marks the past tense if PMB occurs

→ if past is marked by *c-* in position 3., then *x-* is optional (and redundant), yielding *xc-* ~ *c-* (past)

→ initial h of any PM, and the PMA *y-* (3.s/p) are lost when either *ch-* (nonpast) or *x-* (past) immediately precedes

→ nonpast has two allomorphs: *ch-* only before h and y, which are then lost, and before stem-initial '-', yielding *ch'* (see above: affricate-'-cluster); and \ddot{x} - before all other Cs

--in negative sentences with the preposed particle *mach* 'not', one or more proclitics may follow *mach*

→ before *to* 'still' and *tic'a* 'always', *mach* > *ma \ddot{x}* : *ma \ddot{x} to chin wayi* 'I'm still not sleeping'

Verb-future suffix:

--future suffix *-oj* ~ *-a'* ~ *-o'* ~ *-u'* ~ *-'* ~ *-b'*

→ *-oj* with all intransitive and pseudointransitive transitive verb stems

→ *-b'* with transitive verb roots of the form CV

→ *-'* with all other V-final trans. verb stems

→ *-V'* allomorphs with trans. verb roots of the form CVC (*-u'* after roots with the V u, *-o'* after o, and *-a'* after i, e, a)

DERIVATIONAL AFFIXES:

--only one prefix!

Verb derivation:

--REDUPLICATION: Red (C1) 'iterative' consists of reduplication of the first C of a CVC root (it derives intrans. and trans. verbs from several classes of stems)

→ the resulting CC-clusters are sometimes altered according to the morphophonemic statements (see above)

→ if no reduction takes place, -Red (C1) is optionally preceded by open juncture +

→ -Red (C1) must be followed by *-e* or *-on* (derivational affixes), e.g. *cha pitz'pe* 'you squeeze sth. gently several times' (*pitz'a* 'squeeze sth. gently')

Noun derivation:

--COMPOUNDING: many agentives formed from transitive verbs must be followed by an object noun in a compound construction

--compound nouns are stems which occur in the same syntactic positions as simple nouns

--made up of two stems, the second of which is always itself a noun, the first stem can be any stative or verb

--compounds classified according to (1) the type of construction underlying them, and (2) the transformation necessary to derive them

--other compounds can be related to constituents in the same way, but differ semantically from their underlying "sources"

--some productive classes, in which the first element has specifiable affixes and may have clitics; some nonproductive classes with the same form, but from which the affixes and clitics are absent

→ while glosses of compounds in productive classes usually transparent, nonproductive classes usually show semantic specialization

Class 1A:

--productive compound of form PM3-N N

--e.g. *s-chib'eal txitam* 'pork' (*-chib'eal* 'flesh', *txitam* 'pig'); *s-xe' te'* 'tree root' (*xe'* 'root', *te'* 'tree'); *y-ul ña* 'indoors' (lit. 'house-interior'; *-ul* 'interior, inside', *ña* 'house'; *ña* loses its final /h/ in compounds)

--these forms are compound noun stems (not noun phrases) in spite of the fact that their form is nearly that of a third person noun phrase

--they may take prefixed possessor PMA: *hin-schib'eal txitam* 'my pork'

--derived from underlying 3rd person noun phrases of the form PMA3-N NP3, where PMA3 is possessor, N is head of the 3rd person noun-phrase, and NP3 matches the PM

→ to derive the compound, all of the possessor NP3 but its noun head is deleted

→ thus, the compound above are derived from the same underlying forms as NP3 like the following:

s-chib'eal no'txitam 'the pig's flesh'

s-xe' te'te' 'the tree's root'

y-ul te' ñah 'inside the house (the interior of the house)'

Class 1B:

--the nonproductive counterpart of class 1A of the form N. N.

--e.g. *tzak'a'* (< *tza'k'a'*) 'charcoal, coals' (*tza'* 'excrement', *k'a'* 'fire'); *alcal txah* "prayer-mayor" (former town religious official; *alcal* 'mayor', *txah* 'prayer')

--these compounds derived from same sources and in the same manner as class 1A compounds, but with the further deletion of the initial possessor PMA3

--the examples above derived from the same underlying sources as NP3 like the following:

s-tza'k'a' k'a' 'the fire's excrement'
y-alcaxah 'the mayor of prayers'

Class 2A:

--productive class of the form St(=enclitics)N, where St(ative) must be N or Adj, or adjectival forms derived by *-naj* and *-b'il*, *-la* and *-taj*

--e.g. *winaj ch'oc* 'male crow' (*winaj* 'male', *ch'oc* 'crow')
howla tx'i' 'mean dog' (*how* 'mean', *tx'i'* 'dog')
sajla witz 'white hill' (*saj* 'white', *witz* 'hill')
camnaj cheh 'dead horse' (*camnaj* 'dead' from *cami* 'die', *cheh* 'horse')

--compounds derived from underlying sentences with stative verbs, with the form St-Ø (proclitics) NP3

--to derive the compounds, all verb affixes and proclitics (not enclitics) are deleted, and all but the noun head is deleted from NP3

--if St is an adjectival root, the suffix *-la* is attached to it

--the above compounds are derived from the same sources as sentences like:

winaj-Ø no' ch'oc 'the crow is a male'
how-Ø metx tx'i' 'the dog is mean'
saj-Ø naj witz 'the hill is white'
camnaj-Ø no' cheh 'the horse is dead'

Class 2B:

--nonproductive class consists of frozen versions of the previous class

--form: StN, IV (intr. verb)N, or TV (trans. verb)N

--e.g. *how tx'i'* 'rabid dog' (*how* 'mean', *tx'i'* 'dog')
saj witz 'White-hill' (place-name; *saj* 'white', *witz* 'hill')

--derived from the same source as class 2A and in same manner except that any suffix or clitic on the first element is deleted

Class 3A:

--productive class, second element a N, first element a noun derived from TV by one of the following suffixes: *-om* (agentative), *-b'al* (instrumentative), or *-o' ~ '* (gerund)

--many TV roots with the suffixes must be followed by an object noun, forming a compound of the present type

--the nominalized TV may be accompanied by enclitics, as in the first example:

--e.g. *tenom=toj ánma* 'people-pusher' (*ten=toj* 'push sth.', *ánma* 'people')
potx'om txitam 'pig-killer' (*potx'o* 'kill sth.', *txitam* 'pig')
potx'b'al txitam 'pig-killing instrument, place, time'
potx'o' txitam 'pig-killing'

--these compounds derived from the same source as any simple sentence with the appropriate TV and enclitics in the verb phrase (e.g. *ten=toj* for the first example) and with an object NP3 headed by the appropriate noun (e.g. *ánma*)

--to derive the compound, all but the TV stem, enclitics, and the noun head of the object NP3 are deleted, and one of the appropriate nominalizing suffixes is attached to the TV

ch-Ø-in-ten=toj ánma 'I push people'
x-Ø-s-potx'naj no'txitam 'he killed the pig'

Class 3B:

--nonproductive class of the form TV N

--e.g. *-b'oc'wi'* 'hat, head covering' (*b'oc'o* 'wrap sth. sloppily', *-wi'* 'head')
c'ay tza' 'some who keeps losing things' (*c'ay=toj* 'lose sth.', *tza'* 'excrement')
tz'it te' 'bow and arrow' (*tz'ita* 'throw sth. spear-wise', *te'* 'stick')

--these compounds derived from same source as those in 3A and in same manner, except that enclitics and the nominalizing suffixes also deleted

b'oc'b'al wi'e 'instrument, cloth for sloppily wrapping heads'
ch-Ø-in-b'oc' hin-wi' 'I wrap my head sloppily'
c'ayom=toj tza'e 'excrement-loser'
ch-Ø-s-c'ay=toj naj s-tza' 'he loses his excrements'
tz'itb'al=toj te' 'instr. for throwing sticks spearwise'
ch-Ø-s-tz'it=boj naj te' te' 'he throws the stick spearwise'

Class 4:

--productive class, no nonproductive counterpart, form: N N
--e.g. *ac te'* 'two-toned log drum' (local Spanish *tun*, Yucatec *tunkul*, Nahuatl *teponaztli*; *ac* 'turtle', *te'* 'tree, stick, log')
pale nam (kind of black butterfly; *pale* 'priest', *nam* 'butterfly')
cacaw te' (kind of tree resembling cacao tree; *cacaw* 'cacao-tree', *te'* 'tree')

--derived from sentences with stative verbs of the form *haca' N-Ø NP3 NP3* is like a N
--to derive the compounds, all of the SV but N is deleted, and all of NP3 but its own head is deleted

haca' ac-Ø te' te' 'the log is like a turtle'
haca' pale-Ø no'nam 'the butterfly is like a priest'
haca' cacaw-Ø te' te' 'the tree is like the cacao-tree'

Class 5:

--only two noun roots: *-mam* 'father' and *-mi'* 'mother'
--each root must be inflected for possessor or take the suffix *-e* (inherent possession)

--e.g. *hin-mam hin-mi'* 'my parents'
s-mam s-mi' naj 'his parents'
mame mi'e 'parents'

--seem to be derived from NP3 with *b'oj* 'and' like the following:

hin-mam b'oj hin-mi' 'my father and my mother'
s-mam naj b'oj s-mi' 'his father and his mother'
mame b'oj mi'e 'father and mother'

Personal Names:

--combination of a given name and a "nickname" (also patrilineally Spanish surnames, but usually known only by family, friends, neighbors)

--names form compounds whose analysis is uncertain; some seem to be examples of apposition; these and some others are probably derived from underlying sentences with stative verbs, with glosses of the form *X is Y*

--names have the form N N, where the first N is a given name

Āxwan q'uem 'Juan the dwarf'
Manel Sánta Catal 'Manuel from Santa Catarina'
Āxwan ĀxanĀap 'Juan who lives near the Chapel of San Sebastián' (*ĀxanĀap* 'Chapel of San Sebastián')
Tóno Nel 'Antonio son of Manuela'

Other Types:

--other classes of compound nouns poorly represented in the data

--e.g. *tz'um oñ* (kind of thin-skinned avocado - *aguacatillo*; *tz'um* 'skin', *on* 'avocado')
→ *tx'um-Ø s-tz'umal te' oñ* 'the husk of the avocado is skin'

ix cab' 'beeswax' (*ix* 'woman, female', *cab'* 'honey')
→ *ix≠y-et no' cab'* 'the female of the honey'

--a further, and quiet numerous, group of compounds are not analyzable because one or both constituents occur only in compound nouns, never independently

cañal ay in 'praying mantis' (*cañal* 'dance'?)
cheh can (kind of snake; *cheh* 'horse'?)
pacham can elephant (?,?)
sat cañ 'sky' (-*sat* 'surface'?)
tz'in te' 'yucca' (?, *te'* 'tree')

Adjective derivation:

-*la* → compounding suffix with most adjectives when they occur in a type of Adj-N compound; e.g. *cajla ha'* 'hot water' (*caj* 'hot'); *toholla te'* 'straight stick' (*tohol* 'straight')

-*iñ* → animal color used on Adj. when they denote the color of an animal

→ the compounding suffix *-la* does not occur on Adj. with *-iñ*

→ it is related to the N-*iñ* 'exterior of sth.'

→ e.g. *no' cheh≠q'uej'iñ* 'the horse which is black' (*q'uej* 'black'); *saj'iñ tx'i'* 'white dog' (compound noun; *saj* 'white')

CLITICS:

1. VERB CLITICS:

--occur only in verb phrases

--proclitics: occur in all types of verb phrases

--enclitics: occur in all types of verb phrases, except verbal stative phrases (noun or adverb phrase acting as verb phrase)

--some combinations of proclitics also occur independently as part-sentences, e.g. as answers of questions

--when both, pro- and enclitics occur in a verb phrase, proclitics always precede enclitics, although not necessarily immediately, and enclitics are always the last element of the verb to which they are attached

--proclitics may occur before or after the verb, or mixed in with the tense-person prefix of the verb

Enclitics:

--six sequential positions which may be filled by enclitics

--the last two positions filled by special subclasses of enclitics, the directional clitics (usually glossed as directions such as 'up', 'down', 'here', and 'there')

--their use quite similar to English particles like 'up' in 'climb up', 'tie up', and 'call up'

--many verbs whose action necessarily involves directionality almost never occur without a directional clitic

--most enclitics related to intrans. verb roots

--position 1 and 2: one enclitic may occur in each of these positions, in the order listed; each is preceded by an open unwritten juncture: *wej* (plural, exhortative), *na* (suddenly, immediately); e.g. *wayañwej* 'you-all sleep!'

--position 3 and 4: one enclitic may occur in each of these positions, in the order listed; preceded by an open unwritten juncture

→ when occur before a contour, they must be followed by the suffix *-oj* → this

sometimes occurs in other environments as well, and is sometimes optional: *pax* (again, also, back), *can* (once and for all, before doing anything else, be left (in a certain state)); e.g. *cach waypaxoj* 'you slept again'

--position 5: one of the first set of directional clitics occurs here; the suffix *-oj* often occurs after them: *-ic* ~ *-c* (in, against), *-ic'* ~ *-c'* (to the side), *-il* ~ *-l* ~ *-hil* (out, away from), *-a* ~ *-h* ~ *-ha* (up), *-ay* ~ *-y* ~ *-hay* (down)

→ open juncture occurs before a clitic in this position if the result is phonologically permitted, e.g. to yield V + CV but not *VC + V

→ morphophonemics: (1) after Vs, the *-C* allomorph occur; (2) between two Cs, the *-VC* and *-V* allomorphs occur; (3) after Cs and before Vs, the *-VC* and *-V* allomorphs are more common, but *-c* 'in' and *-c'* 'to the side' can also occur here, and *-l* 'out' and *-y* 'down' may occur if the preceding C is /'/; (4) the *-hVC* and *-V* allomorphs occur in free variation in all of the foregoing environments, but tend to occur only in longer forms

--position 6: may be filled by either of the following directional clitics; preceded by open unwritten juncture: *-toj* (there, completely), *-tij* (here)

→ these clitics related to the intrans. verbs *toyi* 'go' and *tita* 'come' and to the demonstratives *tu* 'that' and *ti* 'this'; e.g. *xin tir toj* 'I threw sth. there', *xin ñustuj* 'I burned sth. up (i.e., completely)'

--position 5/6: if none of other directional clitics occur in position 5 and 6, then the directional clitic *-cañ* 'up, suddenly' can occur

→ *-cañ* is probably related to the second constituent of the compound nouns *sat cañ* 'sky' and *yich cañ* 'horizon'

→ unwritten open juncture precedes it

→ e.g. *xin tircañ* 'I threw sth. up', *xin tirpaxcañ* 'I threw sth. up again', *xquin waycañ* 'I went to sleep suddenly'

Proclitics:

--set of morphemes which may occur singly or in combinations

--their meanings in combinations are often not predictable from the meanings of the single morphemes

--when in combination they occur in the order listed below, except that *to* 'still' may follow itself, yielding *toto*

--a usually unwritten open juncture precedes a single proclitic, except *-m-*, or a combination of them:

to 'still', e.g. *oxeb'to* 'still three', *xa* 'already, yet', *ñe* 'only', *tic'a* 'always, habitually, continuously', *c'a* 'too much, more than expected' (antonym of *ñe*), *mi* ~ *-m* 'perhaps'

→ *mi* occurs only between Cs, and before contour, *-m* in all other environments, e.g. *chinmi wayoj* 'perhaps I will sleep', *toxam chach wayoj* 'perhaps you will soon sleep', *toxami* 'perhaps soon (response to above)'

--proclitics occur in one of four distinct positions with respect to the verb or verb-phrase, the selection of which depends on the particular combination of clitics and on the structure of the word or phrase modified by them

(1) all single proclitics, and combinations of proclitics with the structure shown below, occur (A) within the tense-person prefix of affirmative non-imperative intr. and trans. verbs, (B) postposed to the negative particles *mach* and *mat* 'not' when they occur in the verb phrase, (C) postposed to affirmative imperative intr. and trans. and to stative verbs, and (D) postposed to the first stative stem of a verbal stative phrase

→ when both proclitics and enclitics are postposed to a verb, proclitics precede enclitics

(2) all other proclitic combinations occur preposed to any verb phrase or verbal stative phrase they modify; they can also be used independently as abbreviated sentences

Sentence Clitics:

--two sentence clitics, both occur only before contour, except that the particle *xín* 'then' (see below) can occur between sentence clitics and a contour

--when both clitics occur, then in the following order: *-an* (first person exclusive) and *-la* ('see!, imagine that!')

-*an* has a rare allomorph *han*, preceded by open juncture, which is used in very careful speech and, more often, in writing

-*an* can occur postposed to any sentence which contains any first person singular or plural person marker, and occurs only with such sentences; if *-an* accompanies a sentence with a first person plural PM, its gloss is *exclusive*; its absence always implies *inclusive* (e.g. *jatutan* 'our (exc.) house', cf. *jatut* 'our (inc.) house', *choñ wayojan* 'we (exc.) will sleep')

-if *-an* accompanies a sentence with first person singular PM, its gloss is something like *emphasis on first singular*; however, *-an* obligatory at the end of any sentence that contains both first person sing. and any second person markers → most sentences containing a first sing. PM have *-an* (e.g. *chach to watutan* 'you went to my house', *chin wayoj(an)* 'I will sleep')

-*la* often occurs at the end of a sentence which contains the particle *tu* 'that', and is then glossed by Jacaltecs as 'see!' (Spanish *ve*)

-in other uses, *-la* is usually glossed 'imagine that!' (Spanish *fíjate*) (e.g. *hune' naj tu'la* 'that man, see!', *lañan toc'ala* 'only now, imagine that!', *xwil hune' ha cheh tu'anla* 'I saw that horse of yours, see!' (both sentence clitics!))

PARTICLE *xín*

--somewhat similar to French 'donc', Spanish 'pues', German 'doch', and English 'then'

--in general it occurs after (1) sentences, (2) major constituents (e.g. verb phrase, verbal stative phrase in a complex sentence), and (3) words that serve to introduce a major sentence constituent (e.g. subordinating conjunctions such as *cómo* 'since, aspect words such as *lañan* 'continuative', and *b'oj* 'and')

--when *xín* occurs after a sentence with sentence clitics, it follows the sentence clitics (2nd example below)

e.g. *ilwe ha-b'a xín* 'test yourself, then!', *x-qu-in-'apni=an xín* 'I arrived, then', ...*x-Ø-y-Halni ix xín, chub'il c-ach-'apni* '...and she said, then, that you arrived'